

Munir and Nuket's Bud, Petals, and Thorns Model of Inclusivity

Note: The proposal for this model was put forward by Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin and Dr. Nuket Afat in a concise report, under the Turkish Presidency Award in 2021.

According to Munir and Nuket, inclusivity is not *À la carte*. What we observe in practice is a fashionable inclusion. A good number of inclusive educational models exist, which offer inimitable yet middling perspectives. There are differences within differences and conflicts within conflicts- each model carries its own biases and tendencies, often resisting veracities.

There should be universal consensus on inclusivity, followed by contextual accord on inclusive education (acc to type and severity of disability) to cater to the educational needs of the person with disabilities [Note: This model does not offer universal consensus].

This proposed educational model is based on three elements that follow a flexible hierarchy:

Bud: Refers to early childhood education

Petals: Denotes both general and vocational education

Thorns: Refers to the multitude of challenges encountered by individuals with disabilities in their pursuit of education, regardless of the nature or means of those challenges

Early intervention and childhood development programs (for children with and without disabilities)- an alternate route to early education, tailored to meet individual's needs, should be introduced as a compulsory state-mandated program, to support socio-emotional, physical and cognitive development; address developmental delay and improve outcomes; support well-being; increase independence; and support quality of life. The prime goal is to observe development, and offer skills, support, and resources, crucial to prosper and thrive- both in education and society [financial constraint might fence sustainability of this phase].

With program completion, learners may be offered two parallel pathways: general and vocational education. Both must be designed inclusively, innovatively, and contextually.

General education (integrated) may be offered via formal, non-formal, or informal modes. It must focus on any basic literacy (functional, health, value, numeric, language, art, social, digital, and music); cognitive, functional, adaptive, behavioral, social, emotional, and communication skills (+/-). The primary goal is to enhance fundamental competencies and capabilities through personalized learning experiences. A customized approach called Individualized Education Program (IEP) should be devised, utilizing a team-based approach to address individual learning characteristics effectively. Timetable, learning arrangements, instructional strategies, and classroom organization must be adjusted. Teaching children with disabilities alongwith mainstream children can promote socialization, academic success, empathy, and a more accepting and inclusive community. It is recommended to promote disability inclusion, i.e., offer general education in ordinary schools with other learners (integrated education). Inclusive learners may attend regular classes with others, whereas, special support classes should be arranged separately, a few times a week. With frequent progress checks (observation-based), the learner may be shifted or adjusted to another level [Note: Subject to the severity of disability].

Parents of inclusive needs-based learners desire to shift their child's dependencies to independencies. They want them to have skills for successful independent social and financial living. Vocational education (skills-based) offers a sense of accomplishment and personal satisfaction, both for parents and persons with disabilities. Globally, vocational education programs have facilitated inclusive learners toward a successful transition to life. However, vocational training toward self-sufficiency is somehow neglected. In the quest to support inclusive needs-based learners' well-rounded education, for success (operational definition: small accomplishment) in both their personal and professional lives, skills-based vocational education should be offered parallel with general education. Focusing solely on skills that are currently in demand in the labor market may not be sufficient to promote personal self-sufficiency. Instead, it is important to conduct a needs assessment to determine which skills are necessary for each individual based on their learning style, interests, type and severity of disability, capabilities, and prospects. By tailoring skill development to meet individual needs, we can ensure that all individuals have the skills necessary to achieve self-sufficiency.

If, in any case, the learner discontinues general education, s/he must be allowed to continue vocational education.

In this model, the thorns explicitly point to society, in particular, humans, whose tantalizing nature often stings others. The potency of human attack on dignity must not rob tranquility. Therefore, we should work on spreading awareness and acceptance. The concept of thorns-challenges related to accessibility, employment, finance, societal attitude, etc., must be taken

on board throughout the model, so these may be addressed timely and help develop a sense of resilience.

Inclusive vocational education and training units should be set up in rural and urban communities to support elderly disabled people. An inclusive pedagogical approach, i.e., responsiveness to individual needs and abilities without marginalizing those, vulnerable to exclusion, should serve as a method of teaching across all educational institutions.

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